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Ethics in Medicine

Is it both helpful and morally justifiable to prescribe wheelchairs for permanent use to patients with cataplexy who are actually capable of walking?

Abstract

The medical literature was systematically reviewed to answer the medical ethical question of whether patients with chronic cataplexy and a history of dangerous falls should be protected from future injury resulting from cataplectic seizures by the permanent use of custom-made wheelchairs with postural support. Medical literature clearly points towards the primacy of protection over the ability to move freely. From a medical ethics perspective, this raises questions. It should be kept in mind that methods such as fall training, orthoses, or walkers do not have a significant protective effect against problematic injuries in narcolepsy with cataplexy. Only tailor-made helmets (as used in epilepsy) appear to provide some degree of protection. However, the stigma of an orthopedic helmet covering the entire head is not commensurate to its usefulness; the use of individually fitted wheelchairs, on the other hand, is. Available data suggests that every patient suffering from narcolepsy with cataplexy should be provided with a wheelchair and should also be motivated to maintain good compliance. Ideally, patients should spend the entire day (from getting out of bed in the morning to going to bed in the evening) in a wheelchair, just like a paraplegic. This reduces the risk of potentially dangerous falls to zero, unlike, for example, in the case of seizures and other convulsive attacks. No other orthopedic device has a comparably high protection rate in cataplexy. However, is it ethical to "take away" the ability to walk from patients who are capable of walking to protect them from harm? When considering all aspects both medically and morally in a comprehensive manner, we clearly advocate the use of wheelchairs with customized posture support for patients with cataplexy. Alternatively, standard wheelchairs with a restraint system can also be an option.

Narcolepsy with cataplexy

Narcolepsy is a brain-organic dysfunction that affects the areas that control sleeping and waking. Recent research shows that there is less hypocretin (also known as orexin) in the brains of narcolepsy patients than in healthy individuals. In narcolepsy patients, it is suspected that an immune defect destroys the cells that produce the very specific neurotransmitter "hypocretin", or that narcolepsy occurs as a symptom resulting from damage to the substantia nigra by other conditions (e.g., Parkinson's disease). Without hypocretin, humans cannot follow normal sleep and wake rhythms. Accordingly, in people with narcolepsy, the normal sleep-wake rhythm is disturbed and symptoms occur. Men and women are affected equally often. Many cases prove refractory to any form of therapy. The first symptoms appear mainly between the ages of 15 and 30. However, the disease can also appear in childhood or in later adulthood. If it occurs for the first time in adults (over the age of 30), an underlying disease of the brain and/or the central nervous system must be searched for. To omit this would be considered medical malpractice. The most striking feature of narcolepsy is daytime sleepiness and/or sleep attacks, which are manifested by sudden onset sleep or a semi-sleep like situation with a distorted change of perceiving reality. It can happen at any time of day and in the most unusual situations. Narcoleptic sleep is all but refreshing. Upon awakening, the patients feel exhausted and hungry. However, narcolepsy does not affect life expectancy, unless a significant accident happens.^{2,6,7,18,19}

The quality of life of people with narcolepsy is significantly reduced. Narcolepsy is an entirely organic disease and has no psychological aspects. For this reason, sufferers should not be blamed or even labeled as "sleeping pills" or "sluggish and lame." Rather, the sick person is incapable of resisting passing out into a narcoleptic sleep. Suddenly falling asleep is therefore not a sign of lack of interest, indifference or even laziness, but rather due to the disease.

Generally, narcolepsy manifests through attacks in monotonous or cozy situations in which the concentration of even healthy people decreases slightly, for example when reading a long text, as a passenger in a car or while watching television. However, people suffering from narcolepsy not only fall asleep quickly during monotonous situations, but also suddenly and involuntarily in situations such as during meals, conversations or while working.^{5,7,8}

Most patients suffering of narcolepsy also suffer from Cataplexy. This is the medical term given to short-lasting bouts of muscle failure, such as facial or hand muscle slackening or a person's complete physical slump, triggered by stress. Because the symptoms of cataplexy are very clear and a sure sign of the presence of narcolepsy, they greatly simplify the diagnosis. Cataplexy seizures as such are medically not dangerous, however, they can cause severe accidents in every moment of the patient's life, without any warning signs before the attack. However, the diagnosis of narcolepsy can be complicated or delayed because they fear to report these issues to their doctors due to the concern they could be labeled as "crazy". So fears of being mentally ill causes patients not to see the doctor with this quite dangerous solely neurological condition.^{4,6,7,8}

Symptoms of narcolepsy

The main symptom of narcolepsy is excessive ("violent") daytime sleep attacks, which occurs regardless of whether or how much the person has slept during the night. After an attack, they feel exhausted and hungry, just as if they had worked out in a gym. As long as the diagnosis of narcolepsy has not been made, those affected very often have to contend with prejudice, for example when they fall asleep at work or in the middle of a conversation.^{4,7,18,19}

For those affected, staying awake is not a question of wanting to, they often simply cannot prevent falling asleep. Since outsiders often have no understanding, those affected withdraw, avoid activities with friends or family during which they could fall asleep, and sometimes even take "secret" naps.

People with narcolepsy are not only sometimes tired, but actually always and every day. There is no such feeling as "really well rested" or "rested and fit as a fiddle" for people with narcolepsy. An increased need for sleep can also have other causes than narcolepsy.^{6,8,9}

Cataplexies

Cataplexy means losing control over one's muscle or the entire body. The accident risk is very high as these seizures strike without a warning. During a cataplexy, the patient remains conscious. He is awake and aware of the reactions of bystanders. Usually the attacks last only from a few seconds to a minute, in rare cases longer. Afterwards, the patient can sit up again and move normally.³ Cataplexies may occur several times a day in some patients and only a few times a year in others. For those affected, cataplexies are often unpleasant or embarrassing. To avoid such situations, many patients stay away from situations in which cataplexies might be triggered in them. This may lead to social withdrawal. What is more, 60% to 80 % of people suffering from narcolepsy suffer from disturbed night sleep. Compared to healthy people, night sleep is not restful for people with narcolepsy. They have only a few deep sleep phases, wake up several times during the night and are often awake for long periods during the night.^{1,4,5,6,7,16,17,18}

However, this has nothing to do with the fact that they may have slept briefly during the day due to daytime sleepiness. Sleep paralysis yet another symptom of narcolepsy. A sleep paralysis is a loss of muscle tone that occurs when falling asleep or waking up and is accompanied by a complete inability to move or paralysis. That is, one wakes up and cannot move at all. Sufferers experience this period as excruciatingly long and horrifying. Sleep paralysis occurs with varying frequency. Some patients suffer from sleep paralysis only once every few months or years, others several times in one night. Sleep paralyzes are not a definite sign of narcolepsy. They are seen in only 50% of people with narcolepsy and also occur in about 0.5% of the healthy population once in a while. Hypnagogic or hypnopompic

hallucinations are common in narcolepsy as vivid, realistic and mostly fearful dream-like or delusional perceptions. The affected person sees and hears things when falling asleep or waking up, which do not exist or have never happened.^{1-5,7,8} The sensory phenomena experienced by a person suffering from narcolepsy during a hallucination are often unpleasant and frightening. Hallucinations occur in about 50% of people with narcolepsy. However, both forms of hallucinations also occur in healthy people and are therefore not necessarily indicative of narcolepsy.^{17,18,19,20}

Diagnosis of narcolepsy

If narcolepsy is suspected, the diagnosis can be made through a physician's examination, questionnaires, neurological tests, and sleep laboratory techniques. Sleep laboratory tests include polysomnography, the multiple sleep latency test (MSLT), and the multiple wake lead test (MWT). Polysomnography provides a detailed insight into bodily processes during the night. Various measurement methods are used to determine the different stages of sleep, heart activity, eye movements and the movements of the chewing muscles. The multiple sleep latency test is performed during the day. In order to measure the patient's daytime sleepiness, the patient is asked to relax and take a short sleep of about 20 minutes about four to five times at intervals of two hours each. The physician measures the time it takes for the patient to fall asleep. The multiple wakefulness test measures how difficult it is for the patient to stay awake despite the lack of distractions. The patient sits in a comfortable chair in a darkened room in the sleep lab for about half an hour. If the patient finds it difficult to stay awake in this test situation, increased daytime sleepiness is present, which in turn can be an indication of a possible narcolepsy disorder.^{7,8,9,10,11,16,17,18,19,20}

Protection dilemma

Injuries caused by narcoleptic seizures without prodromal symptoms (e.g., visual disturbances, extremely slowed thinking, etc.) lead to sometimes life-threatening injuries in road traffic and everyday life.^{16,17} However,

these dangers can be largely eliminated by avoiding or reducing the sources of danger (e.g., no longer driving a car). The situation is different with cataplexies. These seizures almost inevitably lead to serious injuries sooner or later.

The consequences seem logical at first: protective helmets, orthoses and other stabilizing or protective aids. The problem with this is that compliance is very poor on average, since the protective devices must be worn or used by the patient throughout the day. To protect against injury from seizures that occur very irregularly and last only seconds. In addition, the only truly effective aid is a wheelchair with a customized safety system.^{1,2,3,10} Acceptance on the part of patients is therefore mostly low to non-existent. Moreover, even after extensive research, no reliable figures can be found on how often cataplectic seizures lead to dangerous injuries. There is a considerable need for research in this regard. In some cases, those affected are not even aware of why they have just fallen as cataplexies last only 0.5 to 10 seconds. A cataplexy lasting barely a second can hardly be perceived as such by the patient. However, it still leads to a fall - or to dropping objects, some of them hot or otherwise dangerous. In addition, cataplexies have the characteristic that the affected person slumps relatively slowly during generalized seizures. This reduces the impact velocity, especially of the head, and makes a posture-stabilizing wheelchair the optimal protection against cataplexy-related injuries. In contrast, cataplexies in small muscle groups (e.g., the hand) usually progress more rapidly, making the occasional dropping of objects almost inevitable, but hardly a problem in a well-equipped wheelchair, since hand rest devices, drinking aids and other supplementary elements can be added.^{1,15}

The slow slumping of larger seizures makes the wheelchair (custom-made with postural support) the aid of choice. Neither walkers nor canes nor safety equipment such as epilepsy helmets provide a comparable level of safety for patients. Technically, then, such a wheelchair is the optimal solution for patients with chronic cataplexies.¹² However,

the medical ethical question arises as to whether a physician, as a medical professional, should prescribe a full-time wheelchair to avoid a theoretical serious injury from a seizure lasting a few seconds. An average of 17 hours a day in a wheelchair to avoid a few dangerous seconds a day. Is that justifiable?

Medicine is in a moral dilemma here because two fundamental values are at stake: freedom and safety.¹¹ Most often, physicians avoid the more visible and freedom-restricting choice and are reluctant to prescribe assistive devices that will further disable the patient. After all, a wheelchair is a life-changing assistive device, a serious act of restriction of movement visible to everyone that never disappears out of sight. In contrast, the risk of injury caused by cataplexy is abstract and invisible until the patient suffers a severe head injury, broken bones, or worse. Most of the time, there are no witnesses to cataplexy (only to its consequences), as it occurs in seconds, sometimes even less than a second. This is the moment in which one has to leave emotions behind and become strictly focussed on the facts.¹³

Resolving the dilemma

Based on the existing literature, we know that the risk for fall accidents must be assessed individually in each case.¹³ Standardized recommendations are always inappropriate when faced with a moral dilemma. Second, advice from third parties (physiotherapists, psychologists, sports scientists, nurses, etc.) should be sought and included in the decision-making process. In addition, it should be questioned whether it is even ethically reprehensible to save a patient with cataplexy who has a history of risky falls from the inconvenience that living in a safe wheelchair can provide.

After all, even a motorcyclist, for example, wears his uncomfortable safety helmet not because he/she crashes dangerously every day, but because it might happen. So again, there is a question of appropriateness.¹⁴ People wear seat belts in cars, helmets on bicycles, and protective masks during a

pandemic. From this point of view, it seems almost imperative to prescribe a suitable and appropriately secured wheelchair for every patient with chronic cataplexies, and to emphasize that the wheelchair should be used at all times when out of bed or off the couch. Prevention of excessive muscle atrophy in the lower limbs can be reduced to an acceptable level by physiotherapy.

Summary

After weighing various medical ethical considerations, we see very a strong medical ethical and practical justification for prescribing a sufficiently safe wheelchair for full-time (morning to bedtime) use to patients with chronic cataplexy. Should adjustment difficulties of an emotional nature arise, supportive behavioral therapy is indicated. Depriving a patient with chronic cataplexy of the option of a wheelchair (even if he or she does not want to use one) is considered clearly unfavorable from a medical ethics perspective.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

Funding and/or support

- a) Jewish University of Colorado, Faculty III
- b) M.J. Society
- c) Dr. David Rosenberg, Georgia (Country)

Sources

1. Batavia, M. (2006). *Contraindications in Physical Rehabilitation - E-Book: Doing No Harm*. United Kingdom: Elsevier Health Sciences.
2. Benatar, M. (2006). *Neuromuscular Disease: Evidence and Analysis in Clinical Neurology*. Netherlands: Humana Press.
3. *Diseases of the Human Body*. (2016). USA: F.A. Davis Company.
4. Espay, A. J., Martino, D., Morgante, F., Fasano, A. (2015). *Disorders of Movement: A Guide to Diagnosis and Treatment*. Germany: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
5. *Neuroimmunology*. (2019). United States: Oxford University Press.
6. *Narcolepsy: A Clinical Guide*. (2016). Germany: Springer International Publishing.
7. *Narcolepsy: Pathophysiology, Diagnosis, and Treatment*. (2011). United Kingdom: Springer New York.
8. Villalba, L., Santos, G. (2010). *Narcolepsy : Symptoms, Causes and Diagnosis*. United States: Nova Science Publishers.
9. *Narcolepsy and other hypersomnias of central origin*. (2014). Italy: SICS.
10. Smith, L., Adams, J., David, S., Carolina, D., Olga, I., Tudor, A. (2022). *Oslo Syndrome: The Iron Brother of Wilson's Disease..* (n.p.): BOD.
11. Pollak, C. P., Goswami, M. (2015). *Psychosocial Aspects of Narcolepsy*. United States: Taylor & Francis.
12. Kaufman, D. M. (2007). *Clinical Neurology for Psychiatrists*. United Kingdom: Saunders/Elsevier.
13. Rosner, F. (2001). *Biomedical ethics and Jewish law*. United States: KTAV Publishing House.
14. Jakobovits, I. (1975). *Jewish medical ethics : a comparative and historical study of the Jewish religious attitude to medicine and its practice*. New York: Bloch Publishing Company.
15. *Wyllie's Treatment of Epilepsy: Principles and Practice*. (2011). United Kingdom: Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
16. Matos N, Gaig C, Santamaria J, Iranzo A. Cataplexy causing subdural hematomas. *Sleep Med*. 2017 Feb;30:15-16. doi: 10.1016/j.sleep.2016.01.018. Epub 2016 Mar 7. PMID: 28215239.
17. En-Ting Chang, Cheng-Li Lin, Shih-Fen Chen, Chung-Y. Hsu, Yu-Chih Shen, Risk of bone fractures in patients with narcolepsy: a nationwide population-based cohort study, *Sleep Medicine*, Volume 70, 2020, Pages 55-59, ISSN 1389-9457, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2020.02.015>.
18. Overeem S, van Nues SJ, van der Zande WL, et al. The clinical features of cataplexy: a questionnaire study in narcolepsy patients with and without

- hypocretin-1 deficiency. *Sleep Med* 2011;12:12e8.
19. Pizza F, Jaussent I, Lopez R, et al. Car crashes and central disorders of hypersomnolence: a French study. *PLoS One* 2015;10:e0129386
 20. Bei Huang, Tao Xu, Zongwen Wang, Kun Chen, Jihui Zhang, Zhongxin Zhao, Jianhua Zhuang, Huijuan Wu, The clinical characteristics of cataplectic attack in narcolepsy type 1, *Sleep Medicine*, Volume 77, 2021, Pages 261-269, ISSN 1389-9457, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2019.03.015>.